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Emissions from hot bitumen – Current Eurobitume activities & recommendations

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Introduction

- Eurobitume aims to be the first reference for bitumen in Europe.
- We educate and promote the efficient, economic, effective, safe and sustainable use of refined bitumen.
- Eurobitume and its members are dedicated to safety and reliability at every stage of the handling and use of bitumen, from refining, to transportation, to delivery, and finally to use/disposal.

Emissions from hot bitumen

- **Different perspectives and focus**
- **Specific objectives, aims, methods**
- **Focus today: workplace exposure**

Exposure at workplace

- **Bitumen emissions can contain small quantities of compounds that regulatory agencies have classified as carcinogens or irritants**
- **Measuring exposure has evolved over time:**
 - historically: particulate matter focus
shifted to compounds
- **Interpretation of data depends on methodology and test protocols applied**

Temperatures

- **Temperature is a key determinant for:**
 - the amount and
 - the composition of emissions.
- **Research studies have shown that within the recommended ranges worker exposures are likely to be within regulatory limits and unlikely to be hazardous to health.**

Temperature dependance of amount of emissions

- Paving grade bitumen 50/70
- Amount of emissions depends logarithmically on temperature

Temperature dependance of composition of emissions

- Increase in fume generation temperature led to increase in boiling point distribution of the emissions and a corresponding increase in higher molecular weight compounds
- Increase of 4-6 ring PAH concentration with fume emission temperature

Reminder: Eurobitume recommendation

Updated Eurobitume Technical Guidance on Maximum Safe Handling Temperatures for Bitumen (Paving and Industrial)

For many years, bitumen manufacturers have specified maximum safe handling & storage temperatures for bitumen products, primarily to prevent the formation of flammable atmospheres in heated storage tanks. The maximum handling & storage temperatures vary according to bitumen grade, but the current recommended maximums for bitumen & Air-Rectified bitumen are 200°C and for Severely Oxidised bitumen 230°C¹. Eurobitume has recommended these maximum handling & storage temperatures to its members since at least 1997 and they have been published in a number of documents.

Occupational Exposure Limits (OEL)

- No European OEL on emissions from hot bitumen
- Individual states might have OELs in force – vary by:
 - legal status
 - regulated parameters
 - test methods

Examples of OEL/WEL applied in Europe

- **Germany:**

- OEL on vapours and aerosols from hot straight-run or air-rectified bitumen (paving)
1,5 mg/m³ (STEL 3 mg/m³)
IFA method (bitumen condensate standard)

- **Switzerland:**

- OEL on vapours and aerosols from hot bitumen
5 mg/m³ (STEL 20 mg/m³)
IFA method

- **UK:**

- WEL on asphalt (CAS 8052-42-4), petroleum fumes
5 mg/m³ (STEL 10 mg/m³)

Managing workers exposure and protection

- Temperature control – keep the temperature low
- Risk and hazard assessment per workplace
- Engineering, organisational and protective measures

Managing workers exposure and protection

- **Engineering controls:**

- ground-based truck operations including venting
- remote operations
- respecting wind direction
- local exhaust ventilation

- **Administrative controls:**

- job rotation
- rest periods

- **Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)**

- (respiratory protection)

Most effective

Least effective

Managing H₂S at workplaces

- Eurobitume provides extensive guidance, e.g.:
 - *Potential risks of hydrogen sulphide through the bitumen manufacture and delivery process*
 - *Hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) in bitumen emissions*
 - *Managing H₂S risks during bitumen operations*
- In 2024, guidances were revised with background information from peak measurement campaign in France

The cover of the guidance document features the Eurobitume logo on the left and the title 'HYDROGEN SULPHIDE (H₂S) IN BITUMEN EMISSIONS' on the right. The background is a light grey color with a subtle pattern. The text is in a clean, sans-serif font. The document is intended to provide practical advice on managing H₂S risks in the bitumen industry.

The purpose of this card is to identify the main hazards associated with H₂S in bitumen emissions, the likely exposure scenarios and potential risks associated with it in the context of bitumen loading, discharge, storage, transport and use.

Health and Safety laws impose duties on all relevant stakeholders and on all involved parties to provide safe systems of work.

This guidance is intended to help comply with responsibilities during the loading, delivery, storage, transport and use of bitumen products and is not intended to address legal responsibility of any party. A site-specific hazard, risk and exposure assessment must be completed by the responsible party before any operation or new installation and reviewed if any modification is undertaken.

HAZARDS ASSOCIATED WITH H₂S IN BITUMEN EMISSIONS

H₂S is a naturally occurring gas that can be released from hot bitumen. It is probably best known for its recognizable "rotten eggs" smell that is detectable in very low concentrations:

- H₂S is toxic, acting on the nervous system and can cause irritation to the eyes and respiratory system
- H₂S can deaden the sense of smell, so odour is not a reliable way to detect its presence
- H₂S is highly flammable
- H₂S can react with iron oxide (rust) on the walls and ceilings of tanks to form pyrophoric iron sulphide, a known ignition source in the presence of oxygen.

WHAT ARE THE RISKS?

The risks associated with H₂S in bitumen are:

- Intoxication leading to loss of consciousness which can, in extreme circumstances, be fatal
- Fire or explosion in enclosed or partially enclosed spaces (e.g. tank vapour spaces above hot bitumen)
- Pyrophoric iron sulphide formation in enclosed, or partially enclosed vapour spaces above hot bitumen creating an ignition source.

EXPOSURE POTENTIALS

Exposure to high levels of H₂S can occur when:

- Operating a manhole or hatch of a storage tank or delivery vehicle
- Operating in the vicinity of vents, overflow, or valves
- Inspecting or cleaning empty tanks - remember H₂S is heavier than air and so may be more concentrated in the lower part of the tank

EXPOSURE LIMITS

Exposure limits are country specific, please refer to national legislation. In most European countries the following limits exist:

- The Short-Term Occupational Exposure Limit (STEL, Time Weighted Average over 15 minutes) = 10 ppm.
- The Long-Term Occupational Exposure Limit (LT-EL, Time Weighted Average over 8 hours) = 5 ppm.

MANAGING THE RISK

The following measures should be considered depending upon the outcome of the risk assessment:

- Keep storage temperatures as low as reasonably practical
- Identify areas where H₂S may be present. Provide warning signs and control access to the area where necessary.
- Provision of adequate ventilation or extraction
- Provision of monitoring/detection equipment
- Use of appropriate respiratory protection
- Education of personnel about H₂S
- Use of permits to control entry to confined spaces
- Legislation concerning explosive atmospheres in storage tanks
- Storage tank maintenance programme

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H₂S emissions from hot bitumen

- **Awareness and good working practises are key!**
- **Supporting stakeholders**
 - *Best practice recommendations H₂S*
 - *Communication*

Summary

- **Hot bitumen emits**
- **Emissions are temperature dependent in amount and composition**
- **Eurobitume is proactively working on practical strategies to reduce the consequences of emissions from bitumen**